

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PECULIARITIES OF PHYSICAL REHABILITATION IN PARKINSONISM

Kafara E.,

I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University, Ternopil

Kamyshna I.

MD, PhD, Department of Medical Rehabilitation,

I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University, Ternopil

ABSTRACT

The main stages are considered in the article are elements of physical rehabilitation in Parkinsonism. Also described and analyzed in detail causes, main signs and stages of Parkinson's. The influence of physical exercises has been studied and briefly described, physiotherapy, various rehabilitation techniques (active and passive therapy options) as well as massage for patients with Parkinson's disease.

Keywords: Parkinson's disease, rehabilitation, parkinsonism, physical exercises, physiotherapy, massage.

The aim of the study: determine the main aspects and features of physical rehabilitation of patients with Parkinson's disease.

Materials and methods. Traditionally, rehabilitation methods for Parkinson's disease can be divided into: 1) a complex of various methods of restoration and

maintenance of differentiated motor functions (motor rehabilitation); 2) technologies with virtual reality; 3) cognitive training to improve cognitive functions; 4) social support and psychotherapy; 5) occupational therapy that supports and restores daily life skills; 6) speech correction.

Table 1.

An example of the effectiveness of motor rehabilitation according to research data and a general meta-analysis in the period from 2001 to 2019.

Research in the period 2001-2019. (Held in Germany, France, the Czech Republic) [26-30]	Number of patients	The technique used during the observation	Performance evaluation criteria	Effectiveness of the technique
7 (3- RKD)	132	Active FT, physical therapy with elements of stretching and stretching exercises, increasing flexibility and stability.	Reduction of stiffness of movements, reduction of fear of falling, confidence of movement	There is insufficient evidence for the effectiveness of stretching ratio, increased flexibility, and correction of patient movement.
23 (19 – RKD)	1065	Therapeutic gymnastics, corrective gymnastics, active FT classes.	Motor functions, walking, balance, movement.	A moderate effect of physical exercises on stable position in space, balance and movement, the main effect was recorded on walking and improving the general physical condition of patients.
29 (23- RKD)	1137	A combination of therapeutic gymnastics and alternation during a cycle of 4 classes of active and passive FT	Motor functions, amplitude of movement in joints, walking, balance, movement.	Positive influence on the dynamics of stabilization and restoration of normal movement and walking. Not intense increase and partial restoration of normal movements in the joints (approaching the physiological norm)
12 (12- RKD)	203	Classes on the treadmill	Walking parameters	Positive influence on walking
15 (9- RKD)	369	Combination of corrective gymnastics, static and dynamic dosed strength loads, classes in water	Movement, muscle tone, muscle strength, walking, balance.	Positive dynamics of improving balance after water classes and improving muscle strength after combining exercises have been recorded

Materials and methods of research. Examination of 19 patients with Parkinson's disease. The average age of the examinees in the general group is 62.1 ± 10.9 years old. A general clinical and neurological examination was performed, assessment of motor functions according to the Unified Parkinson's Disease Assessment Scale, neuropsychological testing (MMSE, Montreal Cognitive Test MoCA, depression scale and Beck anxiety scale, Cloninger-TCI psychological questionnaire, scale Berg's equilibrium). All examinations were divided into 2 groups: the first group consists of 10 patients who received standard medical treatment. 9 other patients of the second group were additionally prescribed physical therapy includes exercises for the development of balance and coordination, which was evaluated by using the Berg balance scale. The groups were matched by age, sex, and duration of the disease.

Research evidence has shown that using a series of balance exercises can reduce the number of falls, improve balance control, and reduce stiffness during

walking. The superiority of one complex of balance correction exercises over another complex, their combination is difficult to assess, since the studies differed in the duration and intensity of the classes. In addition, studies have used different scales to assess balance. In one study, balance was improved by reducing the severity of axial movement disorders when a series of exercises to increase the range of motion of the trunk with gradually increasing amplitude was applied. A combination of strength training, massage, and balance training was more effective in reducing postural instability than balance training alone, and water training helped improve muscle strength and joint range of motion. Recently, the effectiveness of combining a complex of physical exercises and balance training with the use of stabilometric platforms for restoring the correct balance to the limits of the physiological norm in Parkinson's disease has been proven.

According to the stage of Parkinson's disease, each of them has certain tasks of physical therapy

Table 2.

Patient management algorithm.

Model A	Hen-Yar Scale 1-2	Tasks: prevention of a sedentary lifestyle, work with the fear of falling, maintenance or improvement of physical activity
Model B	Hen-Yar Scale 3	Tasks: movement, range of motion, walking, muscle strength.
Model C	Hen-Yar Scale 4	Tasks: Minimization of external assistance in movement, improvement of balance, independent walking
Model D	Hen-Yar Scale 5	Tasks: prevention of bedsores, preservation of vital functions of the body, prevention and development of contractures, prevention of pneumonia, prevention of venous thrombosis.

Conclusions:

1. As of today, Parkinson's disease still not studied enough.
2. Physical rehabilitation for this disease can only be complex and developed in a multi-disciplinary team.
3. Massage is considered one of the main means and element of passive influence on muscle tone. Which course should be followed, taking into account concomitant diseases and pathologies of each individual patient.
4. The active part of physical therapy should be started immediately after the initial diagnosis of the pathology. The initial stages do not require a large amount of equipment or simulators.
5. Active physical therapy, depending on the manifestations of the disease, can begin both with working out and restoring the normal walking pattern and increasing the amplitude of movements and mobility of the joints of the upper and lower limbs.
6. Breathing exercises can be used both for general health purposes and for speech and voice correction.

References

1. Agafonova O., Bilyanskyi O. Peculiarities of physical rehabilitation in Parkinson's disease. Sports science of Ukraine. 2014. No. 3 (61). P. 7–11
2. Davydenko K. Parkinson's disease and movement disorders: briefly about the main points. Ukrainian medical spelling. URL: <https://www.umj.com.ua/article/166713/hvoroba-parkinsona-ta-ruhovi-rozladikorotko-pro-golovne>
3. Marchenko O. K. Physical rehabilitation of patients with injuries and diseases of the nervous system: training. manual / OK. Marchenko. Kyiv: Olympic Literature, 2006. 196 p.
4. Pavlova Yu.O. The influence of physical activity on the formation of the quality of life of the elderly. Slobozhan scientific and sports bulletin. Kharkiv: KhDAFK, 2016. No. 1(51). P. 53–56
5. Fedoryshyn L.V., Sanotskyi Y.E., Kardosh N.M. Parkinson's disease: method. river - Lviv: MS Publishing House, 2006. 64 p.
6. Oleksyuk-Nehames A. G., Simkanych N. D. Neurophysiological characteristics of tremor. Actual problems of the development of world science. Kyiv: Center for Scientific Publications, 2016. Part 1. P. 92–94.
7. Cheboraka T. O. Emotional disturbances in patients with Parkinson's disease against the background of comorbid pathology of autoimmune genesis. Scientific journal "ScienceRise: Medical Science". 2018. No. 4 (24). P. 17 – 23.